

Lead firm strategies in the global textile and apparel industry: Are disruptions reconfiguring the geographies of production?

Felix Maile*^{ORCID} and Cornelia Staritz^{ORCID}

Department of Development Studies, Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Vienna, Vienna, 1090, Austria

*Corresponding author. Department of Development Studies, Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Vienna, Sensengasse 3/3/2, Vienna, 1090, Austria. E-mail: felix.maile@univie.ac.at

Abstract

This article examines how disruptions in global production networks (GPNs) reshape lead firm strategies and the geographies of production. We adapt the GPN 2.0 framework by incorporating three mediating factors on lead firm strategy—supplier investment case, path dependencies, and state action. Focusing on textile and apparel GPNs, we find: (1) since the mid-2010s, lead firm strategies have been disrupted by increased online sales and geopolitical tensions; (2) lead firms adapted their sourcing strategies by increasing nearshoring, verticality, and ‘China + 1’ strategies; (3) these strategies materialized in apparel assembly, while production of inputs (fabric, fibers, accessories) remains concentrated in China.

Keywords: global production networks; re/nearshoring; geopolitics; global textile and apparel industry.

JEL classifications: F230 Multinational Firms; International Business; L100 Market Structure, Firm Strategy, and Market Performance: General; L230 Organization of Production.

1. Introduction

The global economy has faced accelerated disruptions in recent years, challenging the stability of the current globalized production model, and fueling expectations for more resilient and “shorter” (more localized and regional) supply chains across many industry publications (e.g. [Alicke et al. 2021](#); [Heidrich et al. 2021](#); [USFIA 2023](#)). These industry discussions echo debates in economic geography, international political economy, and related fields about a possible “bifurcation,” “regionalization” or even “de-globalization” of production networks ([Merino et al. 2021](#); [Gong et al. 2022](#); [Bridge and Faigen 2023](#); [Pietrobelli and Seri 2023](#); [Butollo et al. 2024](#); [Canosa 2024](#); [Hess and Horner 2024](#); [Kalvelage and Tups 2024](#); [Kuang et al. 2024](#); [Yeung 2023, 2024](#)). Although spanning diverse industries, these debates share a similar

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context of disruptions related to climate change and other environmental impacts, digitalization, pandemics, geopolitical tensions, conflicts, and wars, all questioning an organizational and spatial global division of labor that has developed since the mid-1990s. A central theme in these debates is the growing geopolitical tension between the USA and China, which casts doubt on China's position as the global assembly and component hub and as the backbone of the sourcing strategy of many global production network (GPN) lead firms. How do these disruptions and crises shift production and sourcing patterns within global industries? In particular, is the role of China as a key sourcing hub changing? The central contribution of this article is to provide a conceptual framework to investigate and explain processes of geographical restructuring in globalized production and exemplify it through the case of the global textile and apparel (T&A) industry.

The T&A industry is one of the most global and fragmented industries, undergoing significant geographical restructuring since the 1950s, which was mainly driven by lead firms. These firms engage in branding, marketing, and design while outsourcing and offshoring production to a vast global network of supplier firms that handle production of apparel (assembly), textiles (fabrics, yarns), fibers, and/or accessories (Gereffi 1999; Taplin 2014). Since 2000, the T&A industry has doubled its export value (UN Comtrade 2024) and the largest ten T&A lead firms, mainly fashion brands and retailers, quadrupled their revenues (Capital IQ 2023). This growth was fueled by a rapid expansion of physical retail stores in established and new end markets, notably China; the rise of synthetic fibers from fossil fuels; and the rise of China in apparel, textile, and synthetic fiber production, enabling a low-cost supply chain. Recent contributions on T&A GPNs suggest that, since the mid-2010s, the core building blocks underpinning lead firms' established growth models have been increasingly contested. Three processes are highlighted as sources of disruption. First, the industry's traditional reliance on growth through physical retail expansion is being challenged by the rapid rise of online sales, with ultra-fast fashion platforms such as Shein at the forefront of this shift (Lopez et al. 2021; Kuang et al. 2024). Second, the fossil fuel-based apparel production model faces growing pressure from policies addressing climate change and environmental sustainability (Niinimäki et al. 2020; Anguelov 2021; Whitfield and Maile 2024; Joltreau et al. 2025). Third, the heavy dependence of T&A lead firms on China-centered supply chains is increasingly vulnerable to geopolitical tensions, particularly between the USA and China (Butollo et al. 2024).

Against this backdrop, numerous industry publications have suggested that lead firms will adjust their sourcing strategies, potentially reshaping the geography of the T&A industry and China's central role as production hub. The widely cited McKinsey Chief Procurement Officers surveys indicate that 70 per cent of executives have considered moving parts of their supply chains closer to end markets (Heidrich et al. 2021; Magnus et al. 2024). Studies that focus on US brands and retailers conclude that most sourcing officers want to diversify away from China (USFIA 2023). The anticipated changes include a range of processes, including "onshoring," "nearshoring," "verticality," and "China + 1". Onshoring refers to the relocation of apparel assembly to coincide with consumer markets, including "re- and backshoring," which implies that assembly has earlier been performed in a particular country/region. Nearshoring encapsulates moving apparel assembly close to consumer markets, mainly to regional supplier countries, that is, Central America for the USA and North Africa and Central and Eastern Europe for the EU. Regional "verticality" describes the co-location of assembly with textile, fiber, and/or accessories production. Lastly, "China + 1" refers to a strategy in which lead firms source from at least one additional country for each product line sourced from China. These processes focus on the geographical dimension, but they may also entail organizational restructuring, particularly regarding "verticality" which includes geographical verticalization (same country/region but different firm) and organizational verticalization (same firm).

To assess the implications of increased online sales, environmental regulations, and geopolitical tensions for the geographies of production, we first unpack these disruptions and examine their relevance for lead firms' sourcing strategies. Specifically, we analyze whether and how sourcing strategies have changed during the 2010s in light of these disruptions. We then explore how (potentially) shifting lead firm sourcing strategies translate into geographical restructuring, and which factors drive (or constrain)

this process. Of crucial importance is to understand the role of China as the main sourcing hub, given its centrality in the expansion of T&A GPNs in the last 25 years. The article therefore asks: (1) Have online sales, environmental regulations, and geopolitical tensions reshaped T&A lead firm strategies? (2) Have (potentially) shifting lead firm strategies resulted in geographical restructuring? In particular, are T&A GPNs shifting away from China?

Conceptually, we use and adapt the GPN 2.0 framework (Coe and Yeung 2015; [Yeung and Coe 2015](#)) to understand how disruptions impact lead firm strategies. The GPN 2.0 framework puts lead firms' strategic decision-making at the center of analysis and examines how these strategies shape specific firm boundaries, divisions of tasks, sourcing practices, and governance mechanisms. In order to explain whether and to what extent geographical restructuring strategies of lead firms translate to specific shifts in the geographies of production, we incorporate three mediating factors in the framework: (1) "supplier investment case," which refers to (foreign) investment capabilities, financial resources, and incentive structures; (2) "path dependency," which relates to existing asset structures and economies of scale and scope arising from clusters; and (3) "state action," referring to incentives and/or subsidies directly targeted at geographical restructuring of the supply chain. Our conceptual framework is based on iterative theory building linked to the paradigmatic example of the global T&A sector as a largely outsourced industry. It can be applied to other "buyer-driven" industries that are largely based on outsourced production, such as footwear, toys, or furniture. In industries in which lead firms maintain a degree of in-house production, including automotive, electronics, and mining, the two-step framework can be applied to the production stages that are outsourced to supplier networks.

There are three main findings: first, shifts to online sales and geopolitical tensions since the mid-2010s have disrupted lead firms' geographical sourcing strategies. Second, lead firms adjusted their sourcing strategies by increasing demands on nearshoring and verticality as well as on "China + 1". Third, the geographical restructuring strategies have materialized when it comes to apparel assembly, where China lost its dominance. Yet, we find that the production of all inputs (fabric, fibers, accessories) remains centered in China. Lead firm restructuring strategies for these components are limited by high costs for textile mills and fiber production, disincentivizing a supplier investment case. Further, the fiber and fabric ecosystem in China creates path dependencies, as lead firms' product strategies are based on the advantages of China's size, product variety, and low prices for petrochemical fibers and fabrics. Lastly, state action to incentivize the restructuring of fabrics, fibers, and accessories production has been notably limited.

In the next section, we introduce the GPN 2.0 theoretical framework and specify how we adapt it for the specific context of our inquiry, that is, analyzing the materialization of lead firm geographical restructuring strategies. Section 3 outlines our methodology. The rest of the article applies our adapted GPN 2.0 framework to the T&A industry in three steps: Section 4 analyzes T&A lead firm strategies from the 2000s to the mid-2010s (pre-disruptions). Section 5 examines disruptions since the mid-2010s, and their impact on T&A lead firm strategies. Section 6 analyzes how far these strategies translated into geographical restructuring, discussing the role of the three mediating factors emphasized in our framework. The final section concludes, discussing the relevance of the framework for investigating disruptions, lead firm strategies, and geographical restructuring in other industries.

2. Understanding drivers and outcomes of GPN geographical restructuring

The GPN 2.0 framework departs from the assessment that existing frameworks on globalized industries, notably the global value chain (GVC) and the GPN 1.0 framework do not provide causal mechanisms that explain the evolution of GPNs ([Coe and Yeung 2015](#): 21). The GPN 1.0 framework by [Henderson et al. \(2002\)](#) emphasizes three categories (value, power, embeddedness) and four dimensions (firms, sectors, institutions, networks), but it does not specify on the casual mechanisms that (re)shape the connections among them. As a response, GPN 2.0 is presented as a "dynamic" framework through which industrial

change can be explained. The framework therefore provides insights into *why* GPNs are organized and governed in certain ways, explaining the articulation of specific firm boundaries, divisions of tasks, sourcing practices, and governance mechanisms (Coe and Yeung 2015: 21–24).

GPN 2.0 introduces a set of drivers of GPN actors', particularly lead firms', strategies. The first set shaping (lead) firm strategies consists of three competitive dynamics: optimization of cost–capability ratios, sustaining market development, and operating under financial discipline. Additionally, lead firm strategies are shaped by managing a set of risks (economic, product, regulatory, labor, environmental) within and outside GPNs. GPN 2.0 operationalizes how the combination of these factors translates into four generic lead firm strategies that focus on the boundaries of the firm (i.e. which activities are performed internal to the firm or outsourced to suppliers) (Coe and Yeung 2015: 129–57). These strategies include intra-firm coordination (low internal cost–capability ratios, no outsourcing), inter-firm control (generic supplier capabilities, asymmetric lead-supplier firm relations), inter-firm partnership (complementary supplier capabilities, high market imperative), and extra-firm bargaining (social license to operate, regulatory regime, Coe and Yeung 2015: 152–54).

Several authors have claimed that the GPN 2.0 framework faces limitations in serving as a theory of globalized production. Neilson et al. (2018: 420) criticize its deductive nature, focusing on a discrete set of (supposedly) independent variables that determine the dependent variable “firm strategy.” Specifically, it is argued that GPN 2.0 “contains insufficient appreciation of how contextual heterogeneity within different segments of a network acts to constrain lead firm behavior”. Further, there is an emphasis on firm actions at the expense of non-firm actors (labor, civil society, state), and the embeddedness of GPNs within societies and territories (Neilson et al. 2018; Vicol et al. 2019). Critiques have also highlighted the “impoverished” conceptualization of development, which emphasizes a narrow economic perspective while giving insufficient attention to issues central to the GPN 1.0 framework, including distribution, contestation, and power relations (e.g. MacKinnon 2012; Havice and Campling 2013; Bair and Werner 2011; McGrath 2018 for a response see Coe and Yeung 2019; Yeung 2021).

Despite these important critiques, we consider GPN 2.0 and its focus on lead firms as the key coordinators of GPNs as useful to investigate how specific changes in consumer markets, capital markets, and state policies reconfigure GPNs. By emphasizing firm strategies, it opens the black box of lead firms and enables an analysis of the drivers behind their decision-making (Yeung 2021). Our analysis therefore uses the three competitive dynamics and risk environments as key determinants of lead firm strategy, and centers lead firm strategy as the main catalyzer for GPN restructuring. We focus, however, on lead firms' geographical restructuring strategies and how and why they translate into actual geographical restructuring of supplier networks. We propose that the extent to which such strategies materialize depends on three mediating factors.

First, the realization of lead firm restructuring imperatives requires a *supplier investment case*, that is, the extent to which supplier firms possess the (foreign) investment capabilities, financial resources, and incentive structures (i.e. outlook for sustained revenues) necessary to respond to lead firm geographical restructuring strategies. The two generic strategies related to lead firm–supplier relations assume that suppliers neatly integrate into lead firms' GPNs. Inter-firm control requires suppliers to offer low-cost–capability ratios while inter-firm partnership requires higher complementary supplier capabilities (Coe and Yeung 2015: 135–50). Although supplier firms are integrated into the framework, they are depicted primarily as vicarious agents executing lead firms' strategies, without critically examining whether suppliers are able or willing to follow these strategies. Zheng (2024) emphasizes the importance of supplier strategy and capabilities, arguing that lead firms may formulate a strategy without finding suitable suppliers. We argue that the “supplier investment case” depends on the capabilities and willingness of existing or new suppliers to invest in new sourcing locations or the existing asset base to align with lead firms' strategies. Three factors are important for implementing sourcing strategies that involve supply chain restructuring: Suppliers need investment capabilities, which are more likely for large suppliers with existing transnational production portfolios (Gereffi 1999; Appelbaum 2008; Azmeh and Nadvi 2014; Raj-Reichert 2019), and supplier firms need to have the financial resources to undertake these

investments. Finally, there needs to be an incentive structure (i.e. outlook for sustained revenue and profit streams that amortize the investment). Power relations play a central role in determining suppliers' incentive structure as they determine the possibility of capturing value from these new investments. Such possibilities are higher in inter-firm partnership relations than in inter-firm control relations. The latter are common in the T&A sector, which translates into low profit margins, short-term orders, and risk transfer toward suppliers, which has been coined as "supplier squeeze" (Anner 2020). Inter-firm control relations further result in the inability of suppliers to enforce restructuring incentives, such as sourcing commitments made by buyers.

Second, *path dependencies*, that is, the role of existing asset structures and industrial clusters, are important to understand whether and how lead firms can pursue geographical restructuring strategies. Lead firms operate in industries with spatial asset structures that have evolved historically, shaping the sourcing options and ability to reconfigure GPNs. Many industries developed a specific global shape by the late 1990s, creating two main path dependencies: large-scale fixed asset stocks with sunk costs, and cluster effects around economies of scale and scope. The importance of fixed asset stocks has been emphasized by the seminal literature on sunk costs, which emerged in the 1990s. Clark and Wrigley (1995) emphasized that firms' strategies to relocate were ultimately shaped by the height of sunk costs. The literature on evolutionary economic geography (EEG) stresses the importance of historical processes that produce uneven distribution of economic activity and production clusters that are hard to replicate (Boschma and Frenken 2006, 2011). The semiconductor industry exemplifies this with its enormous capital requirements (Yeung 2022). But even in "footloose" industries such as T&A, major assets like textile mills,¹ fiber and accessories production, and transport infrastructure entail substantial financial investments, sunk costs, and cluster effects (Butollo et al. 2024).

Third, *state action* in the form of incentives, subsidies, and trade policy are a crucial factor shaping the extent of geographical restructuring in the supply base. The GPN 2.0 framework focuses predominantly on how lead firms pursue extra-firm bargaining with state actors to influence regulations and secure market access (Coe and Yeung 2015: 151). Yet it underplays how state action is fundamentally interrelated with firm strategies, and with the competitive dynamics and risk environments driving them. We want to emphasize two types of state interventions central for geographical restructuring: first, state policies around global trade infrastructures and end market regulations shape the competitive dynamics and risk environments in which lead firms operate. This includes the physical and legal infrastructure for trade, investments, transport, intellectual property, etc., in consumer and supplier countries. Since the 1990s, this "infrastructure" was conducive to trade expansion. This is now changing in the context of accelerating geopolitical (and military) tensions, with a new scale and quality of state action that aims at sustaining or creating dominant positions in globalized industries, especially for green and digital technologies. Second, targeted policies incentivizing (i.e. tax reduction) and/or subsidizing (i.e. financial handouts) investments into near- or on-shored production facilities have increased in recent years in consumer and supplier countries, notably in the semiconductor and electric vehicle industry (e.g. US Inflation Reduction Act, EU Chips Act, India's Production Linked Incentives). States can play active roles in this through outward-oriented network brokering, extraterritorial institution building, and extraterritorial de-risking to promote "friendshoring" (Kalvelage and Tups 2024). States can further use trade agreements to incorporate geography-related requirements through rules of origin (ROO). ROO specifies which production steps or value shares must be located in beneficiary countries in order to qualify for preferential market access.

Figure 1 summarizes how we adapt the GPN 2.0 framework to analyze and explain the materialization of lead firm geographical restructuring strategies: The evolution of globalized industries is driven by macro factors, including shifts in consumer markets (product and/or geographical end markets), capital

1. A new apparel factory requires capital costs of a minimum of USD 1 million, whereas a new textile mill of at least USD 50 million (Interview 3).

Figure 1 Drivers, mediating factors, and outcomes of lead firm geographical restructuring strategies.

Source: Authors.

markets (shifts in conditions of refinancing, demands of capital markets), state policy (trade, industrial, sustainability, supply chain policies), and technological shifts (in production and or distribution/marketing). The macro factors (re)shape competitive dynamics and the risk environments, which together define the lead firm strategy. In cases where the combination of these dynamics and risk environments drives a lead firm strategy for geographical restructuring of the supply base, the extent to which this strategy materializes remains contingent upon three mediating factors: (1) the supplier investment case; (2) path dependencies; (3) state policies addressing the supply base. Therefore, the lead firm strategy is not sufficient to explain geographical restructuring. Instead, the implementation of lead firm strategy is mediated by the strategies of other actors and institutions, particularly supplier firms, states, and the spatial distribution of asset structures within a given industry (i.e. specific clusters for core components that have grown historically).

3. Methodology

We used a four-layered research strategy combining different data sources and multiple sites in order to examine disruptions, lead firm strategies, and spatial shifts of T&A GPNs. In the first stage, we examined disruptions in T&A GPNs through participating in global industry summits, which addressed the impact of sustainability regulations, online sales, and geopolitics on the T&A industry. These events provided an opportunity to interview firm representatives and experts on the impact of such disruptions on their business strategies.

In the second stage, we analyzed shifting lead firm strategies, focusing on the strategies of the ten largest T&A lead firms by 2022 revenue, which together accounted for USD 195 billion in sourcing volume. We traced their strategies from the early 2000s, with a special focus on shifts since the mid-2010s, in order to understand how lead firms adapt to evolving risks and competitive dynamics. To this end, we reviewed the annual reports of the ten T&A lead firms (all reports 2020 to 2024, and selected pre-2020), and we reviewed coverage on these firms in trade journals and newspapers. Using keywords (“disruptions,” “restructuring,” “nearshoring,” “onshoring,” “verticality,” “China + 1”), we compiled a short dossier for each firm. To track shifts in financial discipline, we drew on the S&P Capital IQ database to collect revenue and profit numbers for each lead firm, as well as financial indicators on inventory and shareholder payouts.

In the third stage, we mapped the spatial restructuring of T&A GPNs. Since comprehensive investment data were unavailable, we compiled investment announcements on onshoring, nearshoring, and verticality from T&A industry magazines. We reviewed reported investments (March 2020–October 2024) in the news archive of Sourcing Journal and Just Style, labelled as “onshoring,” “nearshoring,” or “verticality,” triangulating each announcement with at least one other source. We further noted the stated motivations for each investment. Notably, this way of measuring geographical restructuring is limited to investments that are explicitly labelled as such in industry coverage. To compare the investment announcements against existing global asset stocks, we complemented the investment data with trade data on exports for apparel and for key inputs. We analyzed UN Comtrade apparel, textiles, fibers, and accessories trade data (2000–22). The years 2023 and 2024 were excluded, given that the data were incomplete.

Lastly, we sought to explain why lead firm geographical restructuring strategies succeed (or fail) through interviews with key informants. We conducted twenty-two semi-structured interviews with lead firms, suppliers, and T&A industry experts at global summits (Copenhagen 2021 and 2022; Las Vegas 2023; Milan 2023), in Vietnam, Ethiopia, Kenya, Hong Kong, and online. Hong Kong, as a major sourcing hub, provided insights into sourcing from China, Southeast Asia, and South Asia, while additional interviews captured supplier perspectives and geographical diversification strategies in Vietnam, Ethiopia, and Kenya. The interviews covered the firms’ sourcing strategies, availability of inputs in different countries, and investment decisions. We used the transcripts to build an analytical narrative on why diversification strategies did or did not materialize.

The three-step analysis draws on specific elements of the data. To analyze T&A lead firm strategies pre-disruptions (Section 4), and after disruptions (see Section 5), we use *lead firm-specific data*, including corporate reports, financial data, and interviews with representatives of lead firms. To assess the extent to which these lead firm strategies have translated into geographical restructuring (Section 6), we supplement the lead firm-specific data with *industry-level* investment mapping and trade data, and with interviews with industry experts and suppliers.

4. Lead firm strategies from the 2000s to the mid-2010s: few risks and expanding supply base

From the 2000s to the mid-2010s, apparel lead firms faced minimal constraints in their sourcing networks. Overall, export-oriented development strategies in many supplier countries propelled an increasing number of globally available supplier firms. The business strategies of T&A lead firms were centered around expansion in end markets and capitalizing on hypercompetition in the supply base. By the early 2000s, fast fashion, that is, offering low-cost but fashionable clothing in ever shorter time periods, became the norm, with sales increasing in established and new markets, notably China. Table 1 depicts the largest ten T&A brands and retailers by 2022 revenue, including apparel specialty retailers that operate large numbers of stores and brands that sell most of their goods in department stores. On average, their revenues grew by 388 per cent between 1993 and 2022, with particularly dramatic increases among fast

Table 1. Top ten T&A brands and retailers (2022).

Firm	HQ	Revenue (USD millions)	Number of stores	Number of suppliers	Operating profit (per cent)
Nike ^a	USA	51,217	1,046	388	32
Inditex	Spain	34,982	5,815	1,729	28
Adidas ^a	Germany	24,179	1,990	424	44
H&M	Sweden	20,542	4,465	605	47
Fast Retailing	Japan	15,358	3,592	432	39
GAP	USA	15,616	2,685	Ca. 1,000	42
VF	USA	11,612	ca 1300	808	43
PVH	USA	9,024	N/A	553	47
Ralph Lauren	USA	6,443	344	670	52
Levi's	USA	6,168	1,069	570	46

Source: Annual Reports (number of stores), corporate websites (number of suppliers), Capital IQ database (revenues, profitability).

Note: The firm set excluded high-revenue brands that are part of multi-segment luxury conglomerates and wholesale retailers, given that apparel only accounts for a fraction of their revenue. Therefore, we had to omit LVMH, Kering, Walmart, and Target from the firm set.

^a These firms also produce footwear on a large scale.

fashion firms (H&M, Uniqlo, Inditex) and sportswear companies (Adidas, Nike), while others (Levi's, GAP) experienced rapid growth in the 1990s but have largely stagnated since the early 2000s. All firms have generated substantial operating profit margins above 25 per cent by 2022 (Capital IQ 2023).

Despite lower concentration rates compared to other industries (10 per cent global market share of the top ten lead firms, Marslev 2019), high competition among suppliers enabled lead firms to operate with low *cost-capability ratios* throughout the 2000s and 2010s. Fast fashion requires a “responsive” supply chain to shift rapidly to different styles and reduce lead times (Tokatli 2008; Taplin 2014). Large suppliers expanded their capabilities (speed, flexibility, design) while raising efficiency in assembly, also through developing their own transnational production and sourcing networks (Appelbaum 2008; Azmeh and Nadvi 2014; Raj-Reichert 2019). At the same time, the phaseout of the Multi-Fiber Arrangement (MFA) quota system between 1995 and 2004, and China's entry into the World Trade Organization (WTO) in 2001, accelerated competition between suppliers. Marslev (2019) and Anner (2020) document the extraordinary price depression of apparel exports to the EU and particularly the USA, where real unit values stagnated or declined throughout the mid-1990s to the late 2000s. In contrast, gross margins of the top ten lead firms, that is, the profit margins that lead firms realize on their sourcing costs, rose dramatically from 34 per cent in 1995 to 48 per cent and 52 per cent in 2004 and 2022, respectively (Capital IQ 2023).

The *market imperative* was based on high growth of sales volumes, notably through the expansion of physical retail stores, which grew at a staggering pace: Between 2000 and 2019, Inditex, H&M, and Fast Retailing expanded the number of retail stores by 692 per cent, 744 per cent, and 829 per cent, respectively.² Another strategy, particularly from the 2010s onwards, was expanding in China's consumer market.³ By 2019, the Chinese market accounted for more than 5 per cent of overall sales for all top ten lead firms, and more than 15 per cent for Nike, Adidas, and Fast Retailing.⁴ As a byproduct of this “expansive” market imperative—expanding both the number of styles and stores—retail efficiency declined, reflected in increasing amounts of working capital tied in inventory. Average “days inventory outstanding”,

2. Based on 2000 and 2019 annual reports of Inditex, H&M, and Fast Retailing.

3. The Chinese apparel retail market was estimated at USD 310 billion in 2021. (<https://www.globaldata.com/data-insights/retail-and-wholesale/China-market-size-of-retail-clothing/>).

4. Based on 2019 annual reports of top ten apparel lead firms.

representing the average number of days retailers hold inventory before turning them into sales, increased drastically from 84 days in 2010 to 135 days in 2020 for the top ten lead firms (Capital IQ 2023).

The combination of low cost-capability ratios and the “expansive” market growth model, together with low investment costs, helped accommodating *financial discipline* and keeping shareholders satisfied. Throughout the 2000s and 2010s, net profits could be sustained, and since the mid-2000s, an increasing share of these profits has been captured by extraordinary payouts to shareholders, which rose from 1 per cent of annual revenue in 2000 to 7 per cent in 2019 (Capital IQ 2023). While the US firms largely deployed share buybacks, European firms preferred dividend payments. The decline in inventory efficiency and therefore higher inventory costs and markdowns did not pose financial challenges. This is because low interest rates allowed the top ten lead firms to issue bonds equaling 4.8 per cent of their annual revenue during the period of 2000 to 2020. This surge in bond issuances enabled lead firms raising working capital and financing the expansion of their retail presence. Further, liquidity could be obtained by transferring financial risk to suppliers, whose payment terms increased from 25 days on average in 1995 to more than 50 days throughout the 2010s.

In terms of *risk environments*, the period from the early 2000s until the mid-2010s was characterized by relatively low risks. *Product risks* arising from T&A seasonality and ever-shorter fashion cycles resulted in higher inventory levels but were partially offloaded onto suppliers via short-term and flexible ordering practices. Further, the emergence of new growth segments (i.e. sportswear from the 2000s onwards) and missing out on these segments was an important product risk. *Economic risks* were generally low due to high demand, low interest rates, inflation, and transport costs, and limited supply chain disruptions; the only exception was the global economic crisis in 2008/09, with growth rates abating in its aftermath, but the Chinese market supported continued growth. Further, the financial environment was expansive with favorable access, particularly to bonds. Lead firms could mediate *reputational risks* in terms of low wages and precarious working conditions (“labor risk”) through engaging in voluntary corporate social responsibility (CSR) and multi-stakeholder initiatives (MSIs). Environmental concerns were still marginal in the 1990s and 2000s. *Regulatory risks* were limited with a policy regime supporting global integration through trade policy, legal frameworks, and transport infrastructure. *Geopolitical risks* were low due to China’s WTO entry, the MFA phaseout, and an increasing number of free trade agreements in the 2000s, providing access to an enlarged supply base. Since the early 2010s, there has been a “diversification” narrative, particularly around de-risking from China, but this largely meant adding capacity in other countries instead of reducing China sourcing in absolute terms (UN Comtrade 2024).

Since the mid-2000s, hypercompetition has driven out smaller suppliers, leading to a “bi-frucation” of the supply base. First, large “transnational contractors” from Hong Kong, South Korea, Taiwan, and later Sri Lanka, China, and India have emerged (Appelbaum 2008; Azmeh and Nadvi 2014; Merk 2014; Raj-Reichert 2019). These firms expanded with buyers, took on functions like co-design and logistics, and built their own sourcing networks. They generally avoid marketing, branding, and retailing in established markets, given the high costs and potential competition with buyers. Second, a large group of smaller first-, second-, and third-tier suppliers persists. Some contractors are vertically integrated, but many source textiles from independent mills, which can be nominated by lead firms. Fiber production usually occurs in separate firms, notably chemical firms producing synthetic fibers.

In sum, from the 2000s to the mid-2010s, competitive dynamics and risk environments were favorable to lead firms’ growth strategies. Expanding end markets, access to a low-cost supply base, and limited economic risks all contributed to this context. Just as importantly, minimal regulatory pressures and the near absence of geopolitical risks meant that lead firms faced few constraints in implementing their sourcing strategies. In the next section, we examine three disruptions to the T&A industry that began to emerge by the mid-2010s, whether and how these processes have complicated sourcing strategies, and the ways in which lead firms have adapted their sourcing strategy.

5. The era of disruptions? Lead firm strategies since the mid-2010s

Since the mid-2010s, the growth model of T&A lead firms faced three disruptions. The first is related to end markets, notably the rise of *online retail* in general, and the aggressive expansion of “ultra-fast fashion” retailers since the COVID-19 pandemic, in particular. The largest ultra-fast fashion firm Shein increased its share of the US fast fashion market, measured as the revenues of major fast fashion firms including Inditex, H&M, Forever 21, Fashion Nova, and Asos, from 12 per cent in 2020 to 50 per cent in 2022. A [Deloitte \(2020\)](#) survey across six large apparel markets concluded that the shares of online sales on total apparel and footwear in these countries are expected to increase by more than 40 per cent. Online distribution provides a way of addressing high inventory costs through better forecasting based on consumer data and speed to market. Major e-commerce brands from the UK (ASOS, Boohoo, Pretty Little Thing), as well as Chinese-owned firms such as Shein and Temu (the former headquartered in Singapore), deploy a “test-and-react model.” This model anticipates trends through social media analysis and “heat maps” on their websites, initially producing micro-orders in nearshored or on-shored facilities before scaling up successful items in offshored locations (Interview 17; [ASOS 2021](#); [Lopez et al. 2021](#); [Kuang et al. 2024](#)). Shein exemplifies this by automatically replenishing articles, connecting suppliers to real-time data, and achieving inventory turnover three times higher than its competition, which reduces its unsold inventory to 2 per cent ([Yang et al. 2023](#)). A sourcing manager of an online retailer reported that the “test and react” model yields substantially higher profit margins (Interview 17).

Second, increasing *sustainability regulations* in the three largest end markets (the USA, EU, Japan) require shifts in energy sources, materials, waste management, and production modes across T&A supply chains, given the sector’s high levels of pollution. A first set of regulations focuses on supply chain emissions, setting targets, and requiring progress reporting to reduce emissions and, in some cases, broader environmental impacts, most notably through the EU’s Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive and the US Securities and Exchange Commission’s Climate Disclosure Rule. A second set comprises mandatory supply chain due diligence laws (e.g. France 2017; Germany 2021; EU CSDDD 2024), which primarily address human rights violations but also include provisions requiring lead firms to increase transparency and identify environmental harms and risks in their supply chains, such as pollution, deforestation, and biodiversity loss. The third set of rules is industry-specific and broader in scope, notably the EU Strategy for Sustainable and Circular Textiles, which contains requirements on reparability and recyclability in design, minimum recycling shares, investments into recycling infrastructure, and streamlining of sustainability claims ([EC 2023](#)).

Third, rising *geopolitical tensions* challenge China’s role as the central sourcing hub, which has transformed the debate on “de-risking” toward “de-coupling.” The USA imposed tariffs of 15 per cent on 31 billion T&A products from China in 2019, which it reduced to 7.5 per cent in 2020 ([Lu 2020](#)). The introduction of the Uyghur Forced Labor Prevention Act (UFLPA) by the USA in 2021 escalated trade tensions, with the EU introducing a similar law in 2024, effective by 2027 ([EC 2024](#)). The UFLPA presumes that goods coming from Xinjiang involve forced labor, requiring US importers to prove otherwise. By May 2024, only sixty-five T&A firms of 36,000 estimated T&A manufacturers in China were registered on the entity list ([Homeland Security 2022](#)). The US government has further pushed T&A investments in Central America as part of its “Strategy for Addressing the Root Causes of Migration in Central America” ([US White House 2023](#)). According to the White House, its “Call to Action” of 2021 led to USD 950 million investments by suppliers and sourcing commitments by US buyers in the first 2 years ([Unglesbee 2023](#)). US authorities have flagged Chinese-owned online retailers as “data-risks” similar to other Chinese players such as Huawei or TikTok ([USCC 2023](#)). In February 2025, the US government announced to dispense the “de minimis rule,” previously used by Chinese ultra-fast fashion firms to circumvent tariffs on shipments below USD 800 ([Shalal 2025](#)).

These shifts translate into changes in competitive dynamics and risk environments, reshaping the top ten lead firm strategies. Large shifts occurred in risk environments. *Product risks* remain rather unchanged in terms of seasonality, short-term fashion cycles, and growth markets. But *economic risks* in

terms of overall demand risk linked to high interest rates and inflation (in the context of a tightened financial context) have increased. Additionally, shipping costs and supply chain disruptions have increased, particularly due to the drastic events of the COVID-19 pandemic and the Russian war on Ukraine and related to the looming climate crises. In 2021 shipping costs temporarily increased four-fold and remained at high and volatile levels. Disruptions such as the “Red Sea crisis” and droughts in the Panama Canal, where 51 per cent of all EU apparel goods pass through, caused delays (Rogers 2024). The era of “unlimited” sourcing has become riskier due to increased *regulatory risks*, including regulations related to *reputational risks* (labor, particularly environmental). More importantly, *geopolitical risks* have increased, notably between China and the USA, as seen, for example, in higher tariffs and the UFLPA, and the US blockage of WTO’s dispute settlement mechanism (Maruyama and Wolff 2023).

Cost-capability ratios have changed insofar as the top ten lead firms aim to adjust their sales strategies (increasing online sales) and technologies and materials used in supply chains (less carbon intensive). Cost competition remains largely unchanged or becomes even exacerbated, with new online competitors operating in the low-cost segment. Online sales require supplier capabilities related to multitiered production structures, including onshore distribution networks and to some extent nearshored or on-shored assembly alongside offshore capacities, as well as increased textile verticality (Interviews 10, 17, 19). According to an industry expert, some lead firms have begun to regard verticality (and environmental sustainability) as equally important as labor costs (Interview 8). Especially for the “test and react” model, buyers require that suppliers offer a certain “fabric library,” that is a wider range of textiles for rapidly changing styles (Interview 17). Regarding higher sustainability demands, the top ten lead firms have responded in two areas. First, they increasingly demand use of renewable energy and energy efficiency measures on machinery and facilities from suppliers (Khattak et al. 2015; Khan et al. 2020, Interview 5; Supplementary Appendix 2). Second, some lead firms aim at scaling the share of low-carbon and recyclable fibers.⁵ This includes investments in start-ups focused on recycling blended textile fibers or developing man-made cellulosic and bio-synthetic fibers. However, these efforts have so far not translated into large-scale orders for such novel fibers (Whitfield and Maile 2024).

Large shifts also occurred in the *market imperative*, as growth based on opening new physical retail outlets and expanding into new end markets has abated. For the top ten T&A lead firms, online sales reached 26 per cent of their revenues in 2022,⁶ with numbers of retail stores reaching the peak at the end of the 2010s.⁷ One strategy for addressing overcapacity in physical stores was to repurpose them for integrated channel sales mechanisms (i.e. click and collect) or logistics hubs for online sales. Few large buyers, such as Primark, did forgo online sales for a long time, as they anticipated margins squeezed by high returns. But eventually, Primark also engaged in click and collect sales channels by 2022 (Jack 2022).

Shifts outside the industry have impacted *financial discipline*. Higher interest rates since 2022 have elevated refinancing costs of lead firms via bond issuance, which has made inventory inefficiencies and tied-up working capital costlier. Further, the end of the expansionist market imperative has created challenges in sustaining high shareholder payouts. The imperative to signal liquidity to capital markets was evident during the COVID-19 pandemic, as the top ten lead firms extended supplier payment terms by 33 per cent, improving their cash positions by 30 per cent, and highlighting this shift in investor communications⁸ (Anner 2022; Capital IQ 2023).

In sum, three major processes have disrupted T&A lead firm strategies since the mid-2010s. First, the rapid growth of online retail—driven by new e-commerce players such as Shein and Temu—has

5. Currently, the industry has a recycling content of 1 per cent, with the predominant feedstocks being polyethylene terephthalate bottles (Whitfield and Maile 2024).

6. Based on 2023 annual reports of top ten apparel lead firms. All top ten lead firms’ Annual Reports stated year on year growth for online sales outperforming non-digital sales growth from 2018 to 2021.

7. Ralph Lauren is the only firm that expanded the number of retail stores after the COVID-19 pandemic.

8. For example, H&M increased cash by 33 per cent and PVH by 228 per cent year on year between 2019 and 2020 (Annual Reports 2020).

intensified competition in end markets. Second, a wave of new sustainability regulations in major markets has required lead firms to significantly increase transparency within their supply chains. Third, geopolitical factors have posed the most significant disruptions, particularly the US–China trade war erupting in 2019 and new regulations in the USA and EU that restrict access to textiles sourced from the Xinjiang region.

Table 2 summarizes the changes in the top ten lead firm strategies related to these three disruptions. Overall, the disruptions required lead firms to reconfigure distribution channels (responding to end market stagnation, increasing online sales, dealing with market access risks in China), production processes (introducing partly small batch and flexible production and regional textile verticality to cater for online sales, energy efficiency/renewable energy to reduce emissions), and sourcing locations (de-risking from

Table 2. Top ten T&A lead firm strategies, 2000–25.

Risk environments/ competitive dynamics	2000s to mid-2010s	Mid-2010s to mid-2020s
Risk environments	<i>Medium</i> Few economic risks: Growing global economy, low interest rates, and low inflation. Few reputational risks: Related to labor/working conditions, hedged via voluntary CSR and MSIs Few regulatory risks: “free trade” state infrastructure	<i>High</i> Many economic risks: High interest rates, inflation, higher shipping costs, geopolitics, climate crisis Many reputational risks: Related to environmental harms (transparency requirements, due diligence laws, industry-specific laws) Many regulatory and geopolitical risks: China–US trade war, UFLPA, EU law on Xinjiang, end market access
Cost–capability ratio	<i>Low</i> Low sourcing costs and suppliers increase capabilities linked to fast fashion (quality, speed, flexibility, logistics) Outsourcing capacity provided by growing supplier base (China’s WTO entry, MFA phase out)	<i>Medium</i> Increase in capabilities that require supplier investments (sustainability, small batch production, verticality)
Market imperative	<i>High</i> Growth based on expansion of product portfolio and expansion of physical retail stores Expansion in established and new end markets (China)	<i>Medium</i> Slower growth in end markets Competition from online retailers and increase in online sales “Exhaustion” of emerging market growth and market access risk (China)
Financial discipline	<i>Medium</i> Satisfy capital markets through high profits channeled to shareholders Low refinancing costs through bond issuance	<i>High</i> Continuing shareholder demands but challenges to sustain payouts Higher refinancing costs due to higher interest rates
Lead firm strategy on geographical restructuring	Expansion of global supply base, particularly in Asia Bifurcation of supply base: transnational manufacturers (growing volume and high capabilities) and smaller local suppliers for reserve capacity Limited verticality requirements	Stronger diversification imperative away from China, based on geopolitics (China + 1) Multitiered sourcing structures for online sales Selective regional nearshoring & verticality

(continued)

Table 2. (continued)

Risk environments/ competitive dynamics	2000s to mid-2010s	Mid-2010s to mid-2020s
Materialization of strategy on geographical restructuring	<p><i>Successful</i></p> <p>Transnational apparel suppliers expand to cater lead firms' growth strategies ("supplier investment case")</p> <p>Chinese firms invest in fabric and fiber ecosystem to meet lead firm sourcing strategies ("supplier investment case")</p>	<p><i>Less successful</i></p> <p>Apparel assembly diversification successful: "China + 1" leads to expansion in Vietnam, Cambodia, Bangladesh, led by Chinese firms</p> <p>Nearshoring and verticality strategies less successful:</p> <p>Limited supplier investments in verticality (high costs for fabric investments)</p> <p>Strong path dependencies for synthetic fiber and fabric cluster in China</p> <p>Lack of state action (i.e. subsidies for nearshoring)</p>

Source: Authors.

China). However, only two of these disruptions have led T&A lead firms to adjust their sourcing strategies toward geographical restructuring of their supply base: To accommodate the sourcing strategy to increased (small batch) online sales, lead firms demand more nearshoring and textile verticality closer to the large end markets in Europe and the USA. To hedge against geopolitical disruptions, lead firms are seeking to de-risk from China through accelerated China + 1 sourcing strategies. In contrast, the sustainability regulations do not (yet) have any straightforward implications for lead firms' geographical sourcing strategies. Having discussed how major disruptions in the global T&A industry have changed lead firm strategies since the mid-2010s, we now turn to the evidence on geographical restructuring.

6. Geographical restructuring in T&A GPNs: diversification in apparel assembly, but ongoing centrality of China for fabrics, fibers, and accessories

In this section, we examine whether and to what extent lead firms' geographical restructuring strategies have reshaped the geographies of T&A GPNs. The data are presented in three analytical sub-steps. First, we assess how lead firms' increasing demands for speed and flexibility in online sales have materialized, by tracking investment announcements related to on-shoring, nearshoring, and verticalization using investment data from 2020 to 2024 (Section 6.1). Second, we evaluate the impact of lead firms' strategies on diversifying supply chains away from China by examining shifts in global trade flows across four key stages of T&A production: apparel assembly, fabric production, fiber production, and accessories (Section 6.2). The trade data captures a longer time horizon, starting from 2000 to 2022. We first provide descriptive statistics on investment and trade data in order to understand *what* has changed. We then explain *why* geographies have shifted (or not) through discussing the three mediating factors—*supplier investment case*, *path dependencies*, and *state action* for the different production steps. Third, we analyze the role of Chinese firms in realizing diversification imperatives by examining the foreign investments of Chinese T&A suppliers in "alternative" sourcing locations beyond China (Section 6.3).

In essence, the analysis shows that apparel assembly has increasingly shifted away from China to alternative locations, while production of key components remains centered in China. Lead firm sourcing

strategies on China + 1 and nearshoring did result in a significant diversification of apparel assembly beyond China, benefitting Bangladesh, Vietnam, and Cambodia, and more recently, Central America. These strategies materialized because of the investment case for large suppliers, order commitments by lead firms, and the low capital intensity of assembly operations. State action by the US government to coordinate investments in Central America and trade policies in Vietnam further supported this shift. However, China continues to dominate in fabrics, fibers, and accessories. In this case, the three mediating factors have largely prevented the materialization of lead firms' verticalization strategies: Isolated investment on verticalization in Central America and Vietnam cannot match the size and variety of China's ecosystem. This is due to the high investment costs for textile mills and fiber production, limiting the supplier investment case. Further, China's fabric, fiber, and accessories ecosystem creates significant path dependencies. Lead firms' product strategies are based on the advantages of the Chinese ecosystem, which is difficult to replicate in smaller exporting countries. Lastly, state action to incentivize the restructuring of the supply chain of fabrics, fibers, and accessories has been largely absent.

6.1. Investment announcements in nearshoring, onshoring, and verticality

Table 3 displays the announced investments into nearshoring and onshoring of apparel assembly and regional verticality of textile production based on a systematic media analysis. Since the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020 through October 2024, thirty-four investments in verticality, twenty-three in nearshoring, and eight in onshoring were reported. These are concentrated in Mexico and Central America, with an intention to increase regional verticality in combination with the upscaling of apparel assembly. Most of the investments were driven by a supplier investment case. In Central America, the investments were motivated by transnational suppliers' nearshoring and verticality strategies. For instance, the South Korean firm Hansae co-invested in a yarn spinning mill in Guatemala, an apparel assembly in El Salvador, and entered sourcing agreements with a local synthetic textile mill in the

Table 3. Announced investments on verticality, nearshoring, and onshoring (3/2020–10/2024).

Country	Verticality	Nearshoring	Onshoring
Mexico	4	6	
Haiti		1	
Guatemala	3	3	
Dominican Republic	1	1	
Costa Rica	1	1	
El Salvador	2	3	
Honduras	5	3	
Brazil			1
Peru		1	
USA	8		5
Canada	1		
Sri Lanka	1		
Bangladesh	1		
Vietnam	2		
India			1
Italy	1		
UK			1
Jordan		1	
Egypt	2	3	
Turkey	1		
Total	34	23	8

Source: Based on a keyword search for "verticality," "nearshoring," and "onshoring" in online archives of *Just Style Magazine* and *Sourcing Journal*; 1 March 2020 to 31 October 2024.

Dominican Republic⁹ (Sourcing Journal 2025). In other cases, the sourcing commitments of major US buyers provided an investment case for suppliers. For instance, Target and Columbia Sports committed to place orders from local suppliers by USD 300 and USD 200 million, respectively (Hickman 2023). A number of investments in Central America are further related to policy support in the context of US migration policies. Between 2021 and 2024, the Biden administration promoted foreign investments in the region, with an objective of “addressing root causes of migration” (US White House 2023). In sum, the investment data suggest that a small number of suppliers responded to the geographical restructuring strategies of lead firms, but the number of investments is limited in scope. We now turn to the trade data analysis for each of the production stages in T&A GPNs.

6.2. Changes in trade patterns of apparel, fabrics, fibers, and accessories

The most significant geographical restructuring has occurred in *apparel exports*. Lead firms’ diversification strategies on apparel assembly have therefore materialized. China has dominated the global industry since 2000, but its global share has declined from 43 per cent to 26 per cent between 2010 and 2022 (Fig. 2; Supplementary Appendix 3); for the USA it decreased from 40 per cent to 22 per cent, and for the EU-15 from 31 per cent to 20 per cent (UN Comtrade 2024). The main beneficiaries of the China + 1 strategy were apparel suppliers based in Bangladesh and Vietnam, and to a smaller extent in Cambodia, while EU and US regional suppliers have largely stagnated (Supplementary Appendix 3).¹⁰ In the case of apparel assembly, the mediating factors were conducive to realizing lead firms’ China + 1 strategy. Transnational apparel suppliers expanded in Vietnam and Bangladesh during the 2010s, and the low capital requirements for assembly factories limited path dependencies, given that an assembly plant can be set up for USD 1 million (Interviews 6, 18). Vietnam’s rise as the second-largest apparel hub was further driven by state action. The EU–Vietnam Free Trade Agreement (EVFTA), operational since 2020, and the anticipated Trans-Pacific Partnership (TPP) spurred investments in Vietnam, despite the TPP not materializing after Trump’s 2016 election (Interviews 1; 2; 3).

Despite diversification of apparel assembly, China remains a central apparel sourcing hub. For seven of the top ten lead firms, Chinese-based apparel suppliers account for more than 20 per cent of the supply base, but for none more than 52 per cent.¹¹ Given high efficiency levels, China has remained a cost-competitive location, despite rising wages (Interview 18). This is due to the high complexity of products such as outerwear, which require the efficiency levels of Chinese assembly factories (Interview 22). Additionally, lead firms such as Nike, Adidas, Fast Retailing, and VF source from China to cater to the domestic Chinese consumer market. As a head of sourcing explains, lead firms operate multitier sourcing structures: “We have global capacity, but operate regionally. Turkey and North Africa is for nearshoring to Europe, Central America for the USA. And then we have a large market in China, which we can’t nearshore; so, we still manufacture there” (Interview 10).

When it comes to *textile exports*, China remains the unchallenged center of gravity. China’s share in global fabric exports rose from 13 per cent in 2000 to 44 per cent in 2022. Its share slightly decreased in cotton-based fabrics in recent years, while in synthetic and blended fabrics, which are the dominant fabric categories, China’s share reached 49 per cent and 45 per cent in 2022, respectively (Fig. 3). The UFLPA has important implications, as 85 per cent of China’s cotton comes from Xinjiang, and China accounts for 20 per cent of the global cotton supply. Yet, China remains dominant in synthetic textiles, mainly produced in the Eastern Jiangsu and Zhejiang regions. Fabric production is also dominated by Chinese textile mills. By 2023, six of the top ten, and thirty-six of the top 100 publicly listed firms were headquartered in China (Capital IQ 2023). Many of the top ten apparel export countries rely heavily on textile imports from

9. Hansae also invested in a fabric mill directly in the USA as well as in Vietnam.

10. Regional suppliers to the USA and EU-15 accounted for 4.8 per cent and 12.2 per cent of global apparel exports in 2022, respectively; in the USA they accounted for 16.4 per cent while in the EU-15 for 17.2 per cent, declining from 35.4 per cent and 27.7 per cent in 2000, respectively (UN Comtrade 2024).

11. Based on 2023 annual reports of top ten T&A lead firms.

Figure 2 Top ten global apparel export countries (USD 1,000).

Source: UN Comtrade (2024).

China: By 2022, the share of fabric and yarn imported from China accounted for more than 60 per cent of total textile imports in five countries, more than 50 per cent in one country, and more than 20 per cent in two countries (Supplementary Appendix 4).

Geographical restructuring strategies have had limited impact on fabric sourcing and regional verticality for several reasons. One reason is the supplier investment dynamics, given the high costs of establishing a textile mill, which supplier firm representatives stated at minimum of USD 50 million, and often exceeding USD 200 million (Interviews 6; 18). Further, state action to incentivize the restructuring of fabric production has been largely absent, except in Vietnam, where the EVFTA double transformation (“fabric-forward”) ROO encourages textile investments (Interviews 1, 2, 3; Marslev and Staritz 2023). The main mediating factor limiting spatial restructuring is the path dependency created by the fabric and fiber ecosystem in China. Interviews with suppliers and lead firms suggest that there is no large-scale alternative across a wide range of fabrics (Interviews 19, 20, 21): South Korean mills provide specialty synthetic fabrics for technical and outerwear products, and Taiwanese mills specialize in high-end performance/sportswear fabric. However, China dominates mass market synthetic and “novelty blends” including cotton-cellulose and cotton-spandex fabrics due to its fiber supply chain for these fabric varieties. There are investments in textile capacity in Bangladesh and Vietnam producing synthetic fabrics, which are, however, not supported by a petrochemical sector, limiting variety in synthetics (Interview 22). Thus, de-risking fabric supply from China is limited to certain product categories, such as outerwear and swimwear in Vietnam, high-volume knits in Bangladesh, and dresses in India (Interviews 12, 19, 20; Chua 2024). According to a lead firm fabric manager, only China can meet their changing design demands requiring novel yarn blends and fabric types at short notice (Interview 20).

In textile *fibers*, China occupies a position as important as it does in fabric production. The global textile fiber market is dominated by synthetics, which account for two-thirds of production (54 per cent polyester, 5 per cent nylon, 5 per cent other synthetics), with the remainder consisting mostly of cotton (Textile Exchange 2023). China dominates global synthetic fiber production, although most production is used for domestic yarn spinning. In 2022, China was the largest exporter of synthetic fibers with 17.5 per cent global export share (Supplementary Appendix 5).

China also dominates exports for apparel manufacturing *accessories* (trims, buttons, zippers, hangers) and for specific products such as rubber elastics for sportswear or underwear (Interviews 10, 22). China’s accessories cluster represents more than one-third of export market share across key accessories

Figure 3 Top ten global fabric export countries (USD 1,000).
Source: UN Comtrade (2024).

categories ([Supplementary Appendix 6](#)). No other country exceeds more than 10 per cent export share in any accessory category ([UN Comtrade 2024](#)).

6.3 Investment of Chinese T&A suppliers in “alternative” sourcing locations

Lastly, Chinese T&A suppliers play a dominant role as key investors in “alternative” locations. Chinese firms started outward investments in the 2000s, supported by the “Go Out Strategy” part of the Five-Year Economic Plans since 2001. As [Zhu and Pickles \(2014: 58\)](#) state: “By 2009, nearly 1,000 Chinese apparel enterprises had set up factories in Cambodia and Vietnam and another 100 (or more) Chinese apparel enterprises had invested in Bangladesh.” Since the early 2010s, Vietnam has become a central destination for Chinese T&A investments. Approximately 65 per cent of production volume is generated by foreign companies, with Chinese firms leading, followed by investments from Hong Kong, Taiwan, and South Korea ([Chi 2017](#); [Fibre2Fashion 2024](#); Interview 1). Chinese firms are further central in developing a fabric supply chain in Vietnam, which is however still limited in scale and fabric variety, meeting only 30 per cent of export demand by some estimations ([Global Textile Times 2025](#)). Cambodia’s T&A industry is dominated by Chinese firms. According to Cambodia’s Textile, Apparel and Footwear manufacturer association, 61 per cent of member companies are owned by Chinese investors ([TAFTAC 2025](#)). In Bangladesh, Chinese investments remain relatively limited. In 2024, twenty Chinese T&A firms invested in the country, which is only a small fraction of the approximately 4,500 T&A firms overall ([Hossain and Rayhan 2025](#); [BGMEA 2026](#)). Thus, to an important extent, Chinese firms have facilitated the “China + 1” strategy through apparel assembly investments in Vietnam, Cambodia, and, to a lesser extent, in Bangladesh.

7. Conclusions

Global production networks have faced numerous disruptions in recent years due to climate change, digitalization, pandemics, and, especially, geopolitical tensions. These disruptions have sparked debates among industry analysts as well as economic geographers and political economists about a potential restructuring of the global division of labor established over the past 30 years. Specifically, it is argued that lead firms, as key organizers of globalized production, may need to adjust their sourcing strategies to adapt to disruptions. These debates have become even more relevant given the escalating trade war that unfolded in the summer of 2025.

In this article, we wanted to contribute to this debate by offering one way to study recent disruptions, their effects on lead firm strategies, and the implications for the geographies of production, focusing on the T&A industry, one of the most global and spatially fragmented sectors. Since the early 2000s, T&A lead firms centered their growth on expanding into new consumer markets, notably China, cheap fossil fuel inputs, and low-cost fiber to apparel supply chains in China. In this context, we examined three inter-related processes: (1) Recent key disruptions in T&A GPNs; (2) related changes in lead firm strategies; (3) resulting shifts in the geographies of T&A production, with particular attention on China’s dominant role.

To explore these processes, we developed a conceptual framework that draws on and adapts the GPN 2.0 framework. Central to this framework is the proposition that the implementation of geographical restructuring strategies of lead firms is mediated by three factors—“supplier investment case,” “path dependencies,” and “state action.” We applied this framework to the T&A industry using a methodology that examines lead firm strategies through corporate and industry reports and financial data, assesses geographical restructuring via investment and trade data, and interprets these shifts through interviews with key informants from lead and supplier firms.

Three main findings emerge. First, the rise of online sales and intensified geopolitical tensions affects the geography of sourcing strategies of T&A lead firms. Second, lead firms are responding by demanding nearshoring and verticality from suppliers to meet online sales’ flexibility and speed requirements, and by diversifying their sourcing base away from China for hedging geopolitical tensions. Third, these

geographical restructuring strategies have materialized only for apparel assembly, whereas the production of important components (fabric, fiber, accessories) remains centered in China. This persistence is explained by a lack of a supplier investment case in the capital-intensive fabric and fiber segments, significant path dependencies around the fabric and fiber ecosystem in China, and limited state action to re-engineer fiber–fabric–accessories supply chains.

Our findings have further significance for ongoing debates regarding the analytical merits and limitations of the GPN 2.0 framework. On the one hand, our analysis shows that the three competitive dynamics and risk environments emphasized in GPN 2.0 are useful for explaining the drivers of lead firm behavior and why lead firms adjust their strategies. As outlined in the Section 5, once competitive dynamics—particularly risk environments—shifted in the mid-2010s, T&A lead firms adapted their strategies in response to a changing decision-making environment. On the other hand, our findings indicate that competitive dynamics and risk environments, when understood as discrete causal drivers, are insufficient on their own to account for specific industry network configurations and spatial outcomes, as implied by GPN 2.0. Instead, our results underscore the importance of additional mediating factors that can constrain lead firms' capacity to coordinate and control other network actors. These findings align with prior contributions that have “tested” the theoretical claims of the GPN 2.0 framework and questioned its “deductive capabilities” (Neilson et al. 2018; Vicol et al. 2019; Zheng 2024).

The adapted GPN 2.0 framework proposed in this article can be used to analyze disruptions, shifts in lead firm strategies, and the impacts on geographical restructuring in globalized industries beyond the T&A industry. It is particularly relevant for the automotive, electronics, and mineral industries, where debates around geographical reconfiguration are equally prominent and China plays a key role in input and end markets (Luo and Van Asche 2023; Riofrancos 2023; Butollo et al. 2024). At the same time, geopolitics and related state action to reengineer supply chains are more pronounced in these industries. Unlike in T&A GPNs, many lead firms in the automotive, minerals, and electronics sectors retain substantial in-house production. Therefore, applying our framework to these industries should focus on the geographical restructuring of outsourced manufacturing steps. As a result, the disruptions faced by lead firms and their sourcing strategies may differ, and the three mediating factors may be “stronger” or “weaker” across industries. Nevertheless, we argue that the mechanisms that link disruptions, shifts in lead firm strategies, and geographical restructuring, mediated through the three factors, will be similar. We therefore hope that our contribution helps to explain why and to what extent certain disruptions change the geographies of production in some sectors, while existing geographical configurations are more persistent in other industries.

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Supplementary material

[Supplementary material](#) is available at *Journal of Economic Geography* online.

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Research involving human participants and/or animals

The study involved interviewing human participants. The study was carried out after a self-assessment on research ethics based on the Research Ethics Questionnaire by the Faculty of Social Sciences of the University of Vienna.

Informed consent

Each interview participant was informed of the project in detail and the explicit consent of the participants was obtained prior to the interview.

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